

JIGSAW COOPERATIVE AND FLIPPED CLASSROOM STRATEGIES IN TERTIARY SCHOOLS STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MEIOSIS, AKWAIBOM STATE

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Abstract

Despite the research efforts over the years, students' academic poor performance in the concept of meiosis has continued to persist among tertiary school students. Consequently, this study aims to examine the effect of jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies in facilitating tertiary school students' academic performance in meiosis. In line with the objectives of the study, three research questions were raised to guide the study, and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a quasi-experimental research design with a pre-test and post-test that were non-equivalent. The population of the study was made up of all the 1,240 students offering BIO101 in the two public universities in Akwa Ibom State in 2022/2023 academic section. The study sample size was two hundred and two (202: 101 males and 101 females) undergraduate students in the University of Uyo and Akwa Ibom State University, using the purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher-made fifty (50) multiple-choice performance test tagged: Performance Test on Meiosis (PTM). The instrument was designed to measure the students' pre- and post-tests. The instrument was validated using both face validity and content validity. The data obtained from the pre-test and post-test was analysed using mean, standard deviation, and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analyses showed, among others, that there is no significant difference between the academic performance of biology students taught meiosis using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies; there is a significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught meiosis using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. Also, the findings on the interaction effect of strategies and gender on academic performance of biology students taught meiosis indicated no significant difference. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies have no comparative effect on undergraduate students' performance in meiosis in Akwa Ibom State. It was

recommended, among others, that biology lecturers should adopt jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom teaching strategies, as the strategies for teaching the concept of meiosis in tertiary institutions while also ensuring other difficult topics are taught based on the right teaching methods.

Keywords: Jigsaw cooperative, flipped classroom, tertiary schools, students' academic performance, meiosis

Introduction

Biology is the science of life. It is a branch of natural science that deals with the study of living organisms, their structures, functions, evolution, distribution, and interrelationships. Biology occupies a unique position in the secondary school education curriculum because of its importance as the science of life. Biology is the study of living organisms using the scientific method. It classifies and describes organisms, their functions, how species come into existence, and the interactions they have with each other and with the natural environment. The four unifying principles forming the foundation of modern biology are cell theory, evolution, genetics, and homeostasis. Biology is a science subject that aims at equipping students with the appropriate scientific attitude, competences, and ability to apply scientific knowledge to every challenge of life. Biology as a science subject occupies a central position in the science curriculum (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2021). This is because biology is a (life science) subject concerned with the study of living organisms with regards to their structure, function, growth, evolution, distribution, identification and taxonomy. Okori and Jerry (2018) explained that the study of biology enables man to understand the diversity of life forms, conservation and sustainable use of natural resources.

Eriba and Samuel (2018) highlighted the importance of biology to include: helping individuals to understand the parts of his or her body and their functions; enabling one to question superstition due to sustained interest arising from comprehension of the cause of events; understanding and appreciating life; bringing into focus the need to maintain good health; promoting the individual's choice of career; inculcating in the individual scientific skills and attitudes in his or her approach to personal and societal problems; imparting factual knowledge; and stimulating scientific reflective thinking so as to produce a better informed individual. Due to the importance of biology, much emphasis has been placed on instructional delivery, especially at the secondary school level. This is to assist in memorisation of the principles and objectives of biology education as stipulated by the National Policy on Education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2020). The study of biology in senior secondary schools is

expected to equip students with useful concepts, principles, and theories that will enable them to face the challenges before and after graduation. In spite of the importance of biology, Nigerian students' academic performance in this subject at the senior secondary level has not been encouraging over the years (Mutangana & Mwesigye, 2022).

There are different concepts in biology, and there are ways of teaching them effectively. Some biology topics can sometimes be difficult, especially when describing things that cannot be seen, abstract concepts that cannot be fully comprehended for the first time, or unbelievable it could exist (Haruna, 2021). Some of the topics taught in biology that students perceive as abstract are water transport in plants, protein synthesis, respiration, photosynthesis, gaseous exchange, cells, mitosis and meiosis, organs, physiological processes, hormonal regulation, oxygen transport, genetics, and the central nervous system (WAEC Examination's Report, 2018). Research studies have shown that a number of concepts in biology, which include meiosis, contain some contents that pose difficulty for biology students to understand (Murtonen *et al.*, 2020). Meiosis is considered to be one of the most difficult topics to teach and learn in biology by teachers and students in many parts of the world (Haydar *et al.*, 2020). Students have a lot of misconceptions about meiosis, which act as barriers to understanding the topic.

Meiosis is a cell division in sexually reproducing organisms that reduces the number of chromosomes needed to produce gametes, such as sperm in males and eggs in females. It is a process where a single cell divides twice to produce four cells containing half the original amount of genetic information (Gilchrist, 2022). During meiosis, one cell divides twice to form four daughter cells. These four daughter cells only have half the number of chromosomes of the parent cell, which are haploid. In the human body, the meiosis process takes place to decrease the number of chromosomes in a normal cell (which is 46 chromosomes to 23 chromosomes in eggs and sperm). So the number of chromosomes in meiosis decreases by half. Consequently, during fertilisation, when the two haploid cells fuse, the number of chromosomes in the produced cell is restored as somatic cells, each with 46 chromosomes. Thus, meiosis ensures the conservation of a specific chromosome number after fertilization. Fertilisation involves the fusion of male and female gametes.

Musa (2019) highlighted the following as factors contributing to learning difficulties in meiosis: new terminology like homologous chromosomes, sister chromatids, haploid cells, diploid cells and alleles which can be confusing for students; students do not get adequate and effective explanations necessary to enhance understanding; negative attitude of students belief that meiosis is a difficult concept; students often find it difficult to differentiate between meiosis and mitosis, which can be

confusing as they share similarities but serve different purposes; meiosis is closely related to genetics and inheritance, so students need to connect it to concepts like Mendelian genetics, which adds complexity; lack of practical activities as well as too many similar terms in the topic such as genetic recombination which are not directly observable, making it more abstract and challenging for the students; lack of teaching and learning resources such as video tapes, computer programs and charts to illustrate what was being taught. Thus, difficult aspects of meiosis require the use of appropriate teaching methods such as instructional scaffolding, blended learning strategies, flipped classes, and jigsaw. This is due to the fact that it will give students the opportunity to participate actively in the learning process in order to reduce the level of abstraction of the concept and increase their academic performance in biology (Basil, 2021).

Academic performance is participants' examination grade at the end of a semester, term, or programme. It is the level of performance in a particular field of study. Higher scores indicate better academic performance (Augustine, 2018). Academic performance is measured using classroom exercises, assignments, and continuous assessments, as well as internal and external examinations (Okolocha & Nwaukwa, 2020). Researchers have identified a number of causative factors responsible for students' poor academic performance in biology. For instance, Ndayambaje *et al.* (2021) stated that students' inadequate preparation and poor coverage of the biology syllabus, failure on the part of students to adhere to instructions, lack of understanding of the demands of the question due to poor reading culture, illegible handwriting, and poor spelling; shortage of qualified teachers, inadequate facilities, lack of a good school environment, and examination malpractices. However, mastery of the concept of meiosis might not be fully achieved without the use of instructional teaching strategies. To minimise the failure rate in biology, Awodun *et al.* (2019) and Rahmat *et al.* (2021) recommended that teachers should employ innovative teaching strategies such as jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom learning strategies to encourage students to develop their own knowledge and improve their academic performance.

Jigsaw cooperative is a cooperative learning technique that was developed by Elliot Aronson and his colleagues in 1978. The jigsaw technique was created with the goals of reducing conflict, enhancing positive educational outcomes and helping students realize they are essential components of a whole, thereby encouraging cooperation in a learning environment. In science education, the Jigsaw method and its variants are reported to be used in classes more often than other collaborative learning methods, especially in biology, chemistry, physics, mathematics and the earth sciences. This is because the Jigsaw method is considered to enhance cooperative learning by making each student focus on a particular topic (Jainal & Shahrill, 2021). Jigsaw is a

cooperative learning strategy that ensures that everyone becomes an expert and shares learning so that eventually, all group members know the content. Its benefits are enormous.

Jigsaw cooperative strategy can help students who have less capabilities to be assisted and mentored by students who have higher capabilities. This will create a sense of positive interdependence among the students as well as allow the students to maintain personal responsibility (Hamadneh, 2018). Furthermore, jigsaw cooperative strategy can increase the student's motivation in learning, positive behaviour, and students' achievement (Halimah & Sukmayadi, 2019). Jigsaw cooperative strategy can help students to actively participate in class activities and enhance an active atmosphere in learning (Pahwa, 2022). Despite the many benefits of implementing a jigsaw cooperative strategy in the learning process, however, implementation of a jigsaw cooperative strategy would be more appropriate given to material related to the theory, not formulas (Siti *et al.*, 2020). That is because, theory can be read by students themselves before learning in class begins, so that students have basic knowledge before learning. In a jigsaw cooperative strategy, the teacher organizes learning activities more communicatively, but this does not mean allowing students to learn on their own. The teacher must help students in their learning by becoming actively involved. The teacher's main role is to choose learning materials, arrange groups, explain the nature of cooperative group work, provide a conducive environment for the group work, monitor group work, and assist students in working with these materials (Tarinje, 2018).

Flipped classroom learning is a pedagogical method in which teachers shift direct learning out of the large group learning space or classroom, and move it into the individual learning space, with the help of one of several technologies (Georgia, 2021). Flipped classroom learning refers to a teaching-learning method in which students gain first exposure to new material outside of class, usually via lecture, videos or reading of other assigned material, before the class time is used to do the harder work of assimilating that knowledge, perhaps through problem-solving, discussions, or debates (Wei *et al.*, 2020). In the flipped classroom learning method, teachers record or create videos of themselves or other experts teaching, or download video lessons from internet sites. The videos are available on VCDs, DVDs, internet or other storage devices, for students to access whenever and wherever it is convenient. Lawton (2019) added that the flipped learning classroom requires flexible environments, a shift in learning culture, intentional content, and dedicated and professional educators. It also includes the presentation of materials through digital media and technologies so as to allow students study at their own pace irrespective of their gender.

Tolbert (2020) carried out a comparative study on the use of jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. Results of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the performance scores of students when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. Jeong (2021) and Wulandari (2021) respectively examined the effect of using integrating flipped classroom model and jigsaw to develop students' reading comprehension and critical thinking. Results of the study showed that jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies have significant effects on students' academic performance. Also, Shao and Liu (2021) compared the effect of flipped classrooms and jigsaw cooperative on students' learning performance via meta-analysis. The results indicated that the flipped classroom and jigsaw cooperative can improve students' academic performance. Ikwuka and Okoye (2021) examined differential effects of flipped classroom and gender on academic achievement of continuing education programme students in basic methodology in Nigerian Federal Universities. The result shows that gender is no significant difference in students' achievement in using flipped classroom.

Gender is a wide range of biological, behavioural, physical and mental characteristics regarding to and differentiating the female and male population (Okeke, 2020). Gender and sex are not interchangeable; the term sex refers to the biological distinction between the two genders and cannot change. Hence, gender is an aspect concerning the responsibilities, roles, opportunities, constraints and needs of males and females in all aspects of social context (Omotosho, 2019). It is the different socio-cultural stereotyped roles and responsibilities expected of boys and girls. In recent times, gender related issues in science education have continued to receive serious attention judging from the number of studies done to that effect. Makarova *et al.* (2019) opined that science subjects which include physics, chemistry and mathematics are given masculine outlook by educational practitioners. Some research works have shown contradicting evidences in students' academic performance in science due to gender. For instance, while some researchers such as Irungu *et al.* (2019) as well as Nwosu and Ndanwu (2020) declared that there is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students in biology. Oluwatosin and Ogbeba (2018) found that there is no significant difference in the performance of female biology students when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. Tambaya (2018) also declared, on the hand, that there is no significant difference in the performance of male students in biology, chemistry and physics when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. However, other researchers such as James and Alice (2020), Mwhia (2020), Asante *et al.* (2023) as well as Usman and Mankili (2019) reported gender difference.

Ahiakwo *et al.* (2023) examined the effect of gender on the performance of students in biology using the Jigsaw method. The result showed that there was a significant difference between the mean scores in favour of the males. This showed that the males gained more from the Jigsaw method compared to the females. Contrary to this, Tofi *et al.* (2021) found out that there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught basic science using Jigsaw cooperative learning strategy. Minaz *et al.* (2018) in their study found out that both male and female exposed to flipped classroom method performed equally better. On the contrary, Chiquito *et al.* (2019) in their study found out that female students performed higher than their male counterparts on their exposure to flipped classroom and there was a significant difference in their achievement which means that flipped classroom is gender discriminatory. This inconclusiveness and inconsistency of results on the disparities in the academic performance of males and females, has made it imperative to determine if gender would affect the performance of students taught meiosis using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom instructional strategies on secondary school students' academic performance in Uyo Local Government Area.

Statement of the Problem

One of the problems facing the Nigerian Educational Sector today is the persistent poor performance of students in foundational courses, especially in the sciences and biology is no exception. Semester results published have shown that a high percentage of undergraduate students continue to perform poorly in BIO 101 (General Biology) examination. The poor performance of students in the foundational courses in biology has been associated with poor methods of teaching adopted by lecturers during classroom lecturing. This poor academic performance has generated a lot of concern among parents, stakeholders and researchers in the educational sector. In view to this, researchers in biology have continually sought for better lecturing methods that would provide a bridge between unfamiliar concepts and the knowledge which the student possesses in order to improve students' academic performance in biology. Some of such methods identified by researchers are jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom instructional strategies. Some researchers are of the opinion that jigsaw cooperative strategy improves students' academic performance better than flipped classroom strategy, but other researchers are of the opinion that flipped classroom strategy improves students' academic performance in sciences better than jigsaw cooperative strategy. It is on this basis that the researcher is investigating the comparative effects of jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies on tertiary school students' academic performance in meiosis in Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the comparative effects of jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies on tertiary school students' academic performance in meiosis in Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To compare the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.
- ii. To examine the mean performance scores of male and female students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.
- iii. Determine the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101).

Research Questions

To guide this study, the following research questions were raised:

- i. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies?
- ii. What is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies?
- iii. What is the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101)?

Research Hypotheses

To guide this study, the following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female biology students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.
- iii. There is no significant difference in the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101).

Research Method

The design of the study is quasi-experimental with pre-test, post-test non-equivalent groups. The population is made up of all the 1,240 undergraduate schools students offering biology in two public tertiary institutions of Akwa Ibom State. The sample size of two hundred and two (202: 109 males and 93 females) undergraduate students using purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique was used to select two schools available in the area based on the fact that the tertiary schools have qualified biologists for the selected study. These schools were assigned to experimental groups using random sampling technique. Experimental group one was treated with jigsaw cooperative strategy whereas, experimental group two was treated with flipped classroom strategy. The instrument used for data collection was Performance Test on Meiosis (PTM) developed as pre-test and post-test. The PTM was fifty (50) multiple-choice performance test drawn from the concept of meiosis. Each question had four (4) options - A, B, C and D with only one correct answer (key) and three distracters. The test was composed of two forms; form one was the pre-test while form two was the reshuffled version of the PTM used as post-test test, respectively. The PTM was validated by two content experts in science and further subjected to Kuder Richardson (KR-20) reliability estimate to ascertain the internal consistency coefficient. A reliability coefficient of 0.98 was obtained which shows a higher level of internal consistency of the instrument and hence, it was considered reliable and capable of measuring the intended events in this study.

After selecting the sample schools using purposive sampling technique, the researcher visited and obtained permission from the Head of Department Animal and Environmental Biology to use their students for the research. Each of the class was randomly assigned to Experimental Group one and two, respectively. In the experimental group one, students worked individually to study the given materials and present to the other teams to present what they had learnt. The team members returned to their original groups after presenting their material in the new assigned groups. For the experimental group two, phone, video lessons from internet sites, laptop, copies of research instruments were made available to be used in the flipped classroom. The teaching in two groups was done during the normal class period for BIO 101 (General Biology 1) and in intact class setting. This was to avoid disrupting the school programme. At the end of the treatment session, the reshuffled version of Performance Test on Meiosis (PTM) was administered to the treatment groups as post-test under the supervision of the researcher. This was to help assess the effectiveness of the two teaching strategies investigated. The data obtained from the pre-test and post-test was analysed using Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA), while ANCOVA was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Answering Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies

Methods	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Jigsaw cooperative	101	52.48	7.79	68.25	11.58	15.77
Flipped classroom	101	57.81	10.20	74.85	16.06	17.04

Table 1 shows the mean academic achievement scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. The result shows that biology students taught using jigsaw cooperative gained mean academic achievement score of 15.77, while their counterparts taught using the flipped classroom strategy gained mean performance of 17.04. From this result, it can be deduced that students taught using flipped classroom strategy gained slightly higher academic performance score in meiosis than their counterparts taught using jigsaw cooperative (17.04 versus 15.77). Hence, there is a slight difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies in favour of flipped classroom strategy.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the mean performance scores of male and female biology students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies

Methods	n	Pre-test		Post test		Mean Difference
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Male	93	54.34	8.62	70.32	13.45	15.98
Female	109	55.83	10.08	72.60	15.06	16.77

Table 2 shows the mean academic performance scores of male and female students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. The result reveals that male students gained mean performance of 15.98 in meiosis while female students gained mean performance of 16.77. From this result, it can be deduced that the mean gained in academic performance reported by female (16.77) was slightly higher than that obtained by male students (15.98). Hence, there is a difference in academic performance of male and female biology students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies in favour of female students, though the difference is minimal.

Research Question 3

What is the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students on the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101)?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics showing interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students on the concept of meiosis in General Biology

Methods	Gender	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Difference
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Jigsaw cooperative	Male (n= 43)	51.44	7.04	66.28	8.15	14.84
	Female (n = 43)	53.24	8.28	69.71	13.46	16.47
Flipped classroom	Male (n = 58)	56.84	9.13	73.80	16.00	16.96
	Female (n = 58)	58.76	11.17	74.85	16.06	16.09

Table 3 shows the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology. The result shows that the male students gained mean academic performance score of 14.84 in meiosis using jigsaw cooperative, when flipped classroom strategy was used. They gained mean academic performance of 16.96. This implies that the male students gained a slightly higher mean academic performance in meiosis when taught with the flipped classroom than when taught with Jigsaw cooperative (16.96 versus 14.84). For the female students, the reverse was the case as female students taught with Jigsaw cooperative secured more academic performance gain in meiosis compared with their female counterparts taught using flipped classroom (16.47 versus 16.09). The interaction effect was more pronounced among males than females. This shows some level of evidence of the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students on the concept of meiosis in biology.

Testing the Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA for difference in mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	Decision at $p < 0.05$
Corrected Model	11266.346 ^a	2	5633.173	37.211	0.000	Ho ₁ : is retained
Intercept	4964.193	1	4964.193	32.792	0.000	
Pretest	9063.925	1	9063.925	59.873	0.000	
Teaching methods	325.448	1	325.448	2.150	0.144	
Error	30125.659	199	151.385			
Total Corrected	1075497.000	202				
Total	41392.005	201				

NS - Not significant at $p > 0.05$

Table 5 reveals the summary of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of students' post-test academic achievement in biology when taught with jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. The calculated F-value for the main effect of instructional strategies is at df 1,202 is 2.150, while its corresponding calculated level of significance is 0.144 alpha. This level of significance is greater than 0.05 in which the decision is based, indicating that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. With this observation, null hypothesis 1 was upheld.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students in the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA testing differences in the mean performance scores of male and female biology students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-critical	P-value	Decision at p<0.05
Corrected Model	11003.811	2	5501.906	36.030		0.523	Ho ₂ : is retained
Intercept	4691.971	1	4691.971	30.726	3.94	0.000	
Pretest	10744.367	1	10744.367	70.361		0.288	
Gender	62.913	1	62.913	0.412		0.779	
Error	30388.194	199	152.704				
Total	1075497.000	202					
Corrected Total	41392.005	201					

NS- not significant (p>0.05)

Table 5 reveals the summary of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of students' post-test academic performance of male and female students in meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. The F-calculated of 0.412 was obtained which is not greater than the F-critical of 3.94. The null hypothesis is retained. Hence there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101).

Table 6: Summary of ANCOVA testing the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-calc.	F-critical	P-value	Decision at p<0.05
Corrected Model	11386.370 ^a	4	2846.592	18.689		0.000	Ho ₃ : is not rejected
Intercept	5034.833	1	5034.833	33.056	3.94	0.000	
Pretest	8784.327	1	8784.327	57.673		0.000	
Group	369.333	1	369.333	2.425		0.121	
Sex	95.279	1	95.279	0.626		0.430	
Group * Gender	25.790	1	25.790	0.169		0.681	
Error	30005.635	197	152.313				
Total	1075497.000	202					
Corrected Total	41392.005	201					

Not significant at p>0.05

Table 6 reveals the summary of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) for the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101). The F-calculated of 0.681 was obtained for the interaction effect of the strategies and gender which is not greater than the F-critical of 3.94. The null hypothesis is therefore retained; hence, there is no significant difference in the interaction effect of teaching strategies and gender on the performance of students in the concept of meiosis in General Biology (BIO 101).

Discussion of Findings

As shown in table 5, the F-value $(1, 202) = 2.150$ while the p-value of 0.144 is greater than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis was retained. This indicates that there exists no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students on the concept of meiosis when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. However, the students taught using jigsaw cooperative had a mean gain score of 15.77 compared to those taught with flipped classroom who had 17.04. The non-significant difference might be due to the fact that both strategies are student-centred as they encourage cooperative learning among students. This is in agreement with the study of Tolbert (2020), who found no significant differences in the performance scores of students when taught using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies. The finding of the study is contrary to that of Jeong (2021) and Wulandari (2021), who reported that jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies have significant effects on students' academic performance.

The findings on the difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught genetics using jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom instructional strategies indicated a non-significant difference of gender. However, the female in the flipped classroom group had the mean performance gain score (16.77) in all. The result could be attributed to the two strategies being gender friendly. The findings of the study are in line with that of Oluwatosin and Ogbeba (2017), who found that there is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students offering general biology. However, the finding of the study is contrary to that of Eniajeyu and Fatokun (2014); Nworgu (2014) that reported gender difference.

The findings on the interaction effect of strategies and gender on academic performance of students' taught genetics indicated a non-significant difference.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, there exists no significant difference between the academic performance of biology students taught meiosis using jigsaw cooperative and

those taught meiosis using flipped classroom strategies. It is therefore concluded that jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom strategies have no comparative effect on tertiary school students' academic performance in the concept of meiosis in Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion of the study:

- i. Biology teachers should adopt jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom teaching strategies as the key strategies in teaching the concept of meiosis in secondary schools while also ensuring other difficult topics are taught based on the right teaching methods.
- ii. Teachers should be trained on how to use jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom teaching strategies in the concept of meiosis.
- iii. Curriculum and course specification planners, examination agencies, and government agencies responsible for designing and revising the curriculum should incorporate jigsaw cooperative and flipped classroom teaching strategies in the teaching of biology.

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